
THE NEED OF INFORMATION LITERACY PROGRAMMES IN COLLEGE LIBRARIES IN MODERN ICT ERA

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Abstract:

In modern era, due to advancement of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) the world is changing into a virtual classroom and libraries are changing into information centers. Students are more technology oriented. Students are expected to learn beyond the syllabus. Promoting “Information Literacy” skills at all levels of education is the collective responsibility of teachers and librarians. This article discusses about the concept of information literacy, role of a librarian towards the students and teachers for providing the various information services/ products for achieving information literacy. It covers development of ICT skills by the librarian in the Information Literacy programmes. The paper also describes the use of ICT in the college library and the level of satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

Today, in the 21st century technology is a part of almost every aspect of life and learning. With the changing scenario around the librarian must invariably equipped him /herself with new technologies and developed greater tendency for using the latest information tools for different activities. Those who are reluctant to welcome the new technological changes would lose their identity but will provide excellent opportunities to those who use it.” Today, Technology enables work and communication for business and pleasure often with a strong emphasis on hardware, software, portable devices, and "apps."

However, it is not enough for students to be merely "ICT literate". 21st Century students need a broader literacy that guides the use of these tools and applications. This "literacy with ICT" includes "learning about and choosing ICT to critically, creatively, and ethically use, produce, and communicate." A College librarian plays a very important role as “knowledge navigator” rather than “custodian of libraries. He should motivate the students to develop new skills with the advances in ICT. Hence, it becomes important for the student to develop skills in Information Literacy so that they can identify, evaluate and use relevant information effectively.

WHAT IS LITERACY?

The literacy in its broad sense describes “particular ways of thinking about and doing reading and writing.” It is not only about reading, writing, listening, speaking, viewing and representing. It is also about developing literacy with information and communication technology (ICT).

Literacy is the ability to identify, understand, interpret, create, communicate, compute and use printed and written materials associated with varying contexts. Literacy involves a continuum of learning to enable an individual to achieve his or her goals, to develop his or her knowledge and potential, and to participate fully in the wider society. – UNESCO

WHAT IS A INFORMATION LITERACY ?

Simply we can say that “Information literacy is a set of abilities requiring individuals to recognize when information is needed and have the ability to locate, evaluate and use effectively the needed information Paul G. Zurkowski supposed to be the first, who coined the term "Information Literacy" in 1974 when he was president of the Information Industry Association. In a report to the National Commission on Libraries and Information Science (The Information Service Environment Relationships and Priorities.) Information is not knowledge; it is concepts or ideas which enter a person's field of perception, are evaluated and assimilated reinforcing or changing the individual's concept of reality and/or ability to act. As beauty is in the eye of the beholder, so information is in the mind of the user." Related Paper No. 5"; (www.eric.ed.gov/ERICDocs/data/ericdocs2sql/content_storage_01/0000019b/8_0/36/a8/87.pdf) The American Library Association (ALA) defines the “Information Literacy is a survival skill in the information age and calls for restructuring of the learning process itself rather than the curriculum.

The NFIL describes information literacy as: “the ability to know when there is a need for information, to be able to identify, locate, evaluate, and effectively use that information for the issue or problem at hand The concept of information Literacy built upon and expanded the decades –long efforts of librarians to help their users learn about and how to utilize research tools and materials in their own libraries. Librarians to wanted users to be able to transfer and apply this knowledge to new environments and research tools that were new to them. Information literacy expands this effort beyond libraries and librarians and focuses on the learner, rather than the researcher. The current environment provides an opportunity for librarians to play a key role in the evolution of an integrated information literacy curriculum.

INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY (ICT) IN LIBRARIES

Emerging ICTs have changed traditional libraries into knowledge centres and librarians function more like consulting information engineers or knowledge managers (Sampath Kumar & Biradar, 2010) Recent advances in IT have not only increased tremendously the ability to access, store and, functioning process information within the library but also have brought significant changes in the concept, organisation and management of library and information systems (Peyala, 2011)

Information and communication technologies (ICT) facilitate the process The library and information science professionals are utilizing ICT to keep pace with the problem of information explosion. The benefit of instant access to digital information is the most distinguishing attribute of the information. Information technology has transformed the whole world into a global village with a global economy, which is increasingly dependent on the creative management and distribution of information. The impact of ICT characterized on information services by changes in format, contents and method of production and delivery

of information products. The emergence of the internet as the largest repository of information and knowledge, changed the role of library and information science professionals from intermediary to facilitator, new tools for dissemination of information and shift from physical to virtual services environment and extinction of some conventional information services and emergence of new and innovational web based.

BENEFITS OF ICT BASED PRODUCTS & SERVICES IN LIBRARIES:

The ICT products & services are beneficial for the libraries in the following ways:

1. It provides efficient and accurate services;
2. It saves the time, space, energy and resources;
3. It helps for controlling the tremendous escalation of information;
4. It assist to provide high quality of services and increases the range of services;
5. It has invented the ways of resource sharing by co-operation and co-ordination;
6. It helps for the betterment of library image by providing better services in modern way

Following are the some of the technology, which shows the development in the area of library in ICT environment.

- Internet
- Electronic mail
- RFID
- Database
- Blog
- Portals
- Reprography Microfilms
- Wireless technology
- Digital Library
- Library consortia
- Six Sigma
- J-Store
- E-Publication

WHAT IS LITERACY WITH ICT?

Literacy with Information and Communication Technology (LwICT) means thinking critically and creatively, about information and about communication, as citizens of the global community, while using ICT responsibly and ethically.

This representation shows the relationship between ICT literacy (i.e., demonstrating ICT skills) and literacy with ICT (i.e., thinking critically and creatively, about information and communication, as citizens of the global community, while using ICT responsibly and ethically). ICT literacy is a critical component of literacy with ICT, but it is not sufficient in itself.

THE PRESENT SCENARIO OF COLLEGE LIBRARIAN IN ICT ERA

Librarian plays an important role in education process by making users aware of need and motivating the use of information. Information and communication Technologies (ICT) have changed the complete scenario in libraries. Now a day, library has become point of resource-based learning the role of librarian is changing radically with skills of education paradigms. The impact of moving from text based learning to resource based learning will involve heavier use of library materials and a demand for more and a varied media resources, including print and non-print. The librarian is responsible for locating, acquiring, disseminating and tracking information resources of many types. It might include database searching, interlibrary loans, monitoring internet newgroups or maintenance of a computerized library information system. Libraries and Librarians play an important role in reduction of people for effective and efficient information use by teaching them information skills at all levels of education to enable to be informed citizens of the country.

The services given to its users in a library differ from one library to another, depending on the type of library, the type of patrons and the parent body's objectives. The library services as emphasised by Idowu (2011) include:

- Reference Service
- Current Awareness Services (CAS)
- Selective Dissemination of Information (SDI)
- Reprographic Service
- Exhibition and Display
- Technical Services
- Serials Control
- Computerized Interactive Search

- Borrowing, Renewing and Reserving

Here the focus is on the role of a librarian towards the students and teachers for providing the following information services/ products for achieving information literacy.

Orientation programme

This is a training given by the library staff to its users introducing the general techniques of library usage, services/facilities available and to the organizational layout. During orientation library staff delivers a lecture, which introduces the program, demonstrates the use of the catalogue and shows students how to access the self-paced on-line tutorial.. They are able to create a network account and configure and e-mail account during one of their orientation sessions.

Library Brochures

Some libraries publish user manual such as “ Know Your Library”, “ Our Library” etc in the form of Publication of Library Handbook/ brochures for the users which gives detailed information regarding the library.

College Prospectus

College prospectus is the main source which contains the detailed and latest information about the library which includes information regarding the procedure process, collection, services, rules and regulation about the library facilities etc. in college prospectus It is the responsibility of Librarian to update the same every year.

E- Information Literacy

To make aware the users about the network technology with multimedia, digital storage , digital delivery , OPAC, Library software and online sources etc. available in the library

Provision of extension services

The librarian should constantly keep in touch with changes in curriculum and in other educational environment and design services which will ensures libraries growth and contribution in the activities of the college. There are a number of extension services which will help in information literacy programmes.

Web Page/ Web site for college and library

It is the responsibility of the college librarian to design an exclusive web page in the web site of the college. There should be a separate web site of the library. Through the web page or website library can provide the following information to the users .

It gives information about the Special services provided by the library

List of New arrivals

- i. List of books whenever there is a special occasion such as a national event, special course lectures on special subjects. Besides, the relevant books must be displayed with detailed information.
- ii. To render such as providing vital information useful to students
- iii. Information about the scholarship and free ship, etc. to the students

- iv. Advertisement for recruitment and career guidance information
- v. To prepare List of collections of local interest, including documents written by local persons.
- vi. List of Books for the students for completion of their project work
- vii. Prepare bibliographic details either in response or in anticipation.
- viii. Scanned documents appeared in periodicals, newspapers, written by the students and displayed on the web page
- ix. Online library facility given to the external students for examination and also passed out students
- x. Question paper sets of previous years and syllabus made available for the students with the help of web page or website.

E- resources and related services

Which include

- E- Books
- E- Journals
- OPAC/Web-OPAC
- Abstracting and indexing services
- Selective dissemination information
- Current Awareness Service
- Online Services e.g N-List Programme of INFLIBNET, Google Alert etc.

Other Services

- Introducing non – book material, etc. CD-ROM, maps, charts etc.
- Provision of Journals, newspaper etc stresses the importance of the latest information.
- Keep a suggestion box or books in the library to expecting a better opportunity to serve.
- Reprography or photocopy facility should be made available.
- Library should produce its own selective abstracting service if it is not possible to acquire abstracting journals.
- College librarian should take interest in establishment of a bookshop on the campus.
- Inter- library loan facility should be provides.
- College librarian should implement modern technology and devices in the library operation and service provision to save the time of the library.
- Library should be open for maximum hours and during holidays sufficient reading material should be made available.
- Book Bank facility should be provided to the students.
- A Selected group of the students may be given short intensive courses and literature searching skills in their chosen subject.

The librarian is the most important person in the information literacy programme. Role of libraries and librarian is not only to produce, manage and provide access to information but also

- a) Teaching library or information skills of identifying, locating and evaluating information.
- b) Encourage and facilitate lifelong learning.
- c) Empower students in pursuit of Knowledge.

In this way librarians can certainly enhance the relevance of our profession, but the main purpose is to communicate skills which we have developed already, to perform well professionally, and to offer services of excellence to our users.

CONCLUSION

The academic libraries and implicitly all educational structures faced with challenges due to the new information and communication development and changes that affect every educational program and process. In present educational reforms are taking place in all the countries to improve educational outcomes and these developments causing major changes.. In this context librarians must maximize their potential to be in the position to assume their role in the teaching and learning process. Each academic Library has to develop educational strategies and learning resources to help students develop information It is necessary to have an active and continuing program concerning information access, developed and supported by the faculty's makers, librarians and other information providers because we must be willing to promote and share our experience in this information age in support of our institutional educational mission.

The general perception that "One Size Fits all" is not valid in the case of information literacy. It is true that information literacy is a tool for lifelong learning and knowledge management, But we must always remember that all human beings are not equally intelligent . Hence we must learn to take cognizance of individual information gaps and learning facilities and adopt holistic approach to information literacy It should starts with the learner at the centre stage interacting local sites of information and then extending his reach to the sources of information available across the globe.

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